

AN INSIGHT INTO THE SOCIO-POLITICAL QUAGMIRE IN THE AFRICAN NOVEL: AN ANALYSIS OF WALE OKEDIRAN'S *STRANGE ENCOUNTERS*.

Ogbeide Festus Osaro

Department of English,
Faculty of Arts,
Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma,

Abstract

This study examines the socio-political quagmire and the African novel using *Strange Encounters* as a case study. The study reveals the plethora of societal problems undermining the growth and development in Africa. It shows clearly the mechanisms through which these problems are being carried out and also, suggests possible ways of eradicating these predicaments and their lingering effects on the populace.

Keywords: Quagmire, Socio-political

Introduction

African writers started their expressions of disgust on the various social, political, religious cultural and economic problems bedeviling the African Society. Before independence, African literary writers wrote in protest of colonialism, but the tone of their works changed immediately after independence. This was a result of the activities of the neo-imperialists, our so-called brothers who took over the mantle of leadership from the colonial masters. It is on this premise that this study discusses the socio-political quagmire in the African novel using Wale Okediran's *Strange Encounters*.

Gaining Independence by most African countries since the late 1950s finally placed the independent countries on a pedestal of self-rule. The discovery of this new status necessitated a change. In my master's thesis, "this new status necessitated a momentous avenue for the African citizens to start enjoying the benefits of independence such as good roads, employment, good governance, potable water and electricity" (1).

However, the rivers became the case as their high hopes were dashed. This is why D. S Izevbaye opines that:

Who are the achievements of national Independence the African eagle might be said to have discovered his identity but has also become a vulture to his unkind...writers have come to regard the new rule as no better than the oppressive colonizer. (53)

As a result, to better their lives since the new rulers have neglected the plights of the citizens, the youths now decide to be lawless. Supporting this idea, Benji Egede and Christopher Anyaokwu in "Migration and Social Mobility in Chimamanda Adichie's *Americanah*" say that:

Most of these social movements were either forced violently or voluntary. The involvement of the youths in all these social problems is as a result of the prevailing conditions of want and need light for shed upon the People by their leaders".(46)

In agreement with this poser, Agho states that:

Confronted by an employment for hurting with the attendance task of survival many otherwise well-bred Nigerian girls and even university graduates and undergraduates have taken to prostitution as an avenue for survival. (76).

In response to these problems, African literary writers have equally come out fearlessly to locate and propose solutions in order to reverse this socio-political status quo.

Socio-political Quagmire In Wale Okediran's Strange Encounters

An Insight into the moral decadence of the people of the northern part of Nigeria might have been evocatively presented in Okediran's Strange Encounters. In this text, Okediran flays the criminal attitude of the Nigerian police while at the same time showing the grouse and ignorance of the people of the northern part of Nigeria. Religious hypocrisy, pretense and fraudulent practices are not left out. He satirizes the priests, religious leaders, and even the Christian world for not playing the role of being a model for others to imitate.

In this text, Father Raleigh and Reverend Sisters Martha and Castello represent the members of the religious congregation that the secular members look upon in the society as the spiritual leaders of the people. They are saddled with the privileges, rights and authority to accomplish their task for the spiritual growth of the people.

Reverend Father Raleigh and the two Reverend Sisters are seen by the congregation and the entire members of the society as devoted Christians who adhere strictly to religious doctrines. On the other hand, the reverse is always the case as presented in this text. These so-called devotees are involved in sexual immorality, aiding and abetting evil practices, drinking and lying, etc. Apart from the fact that Father Raleigh maintains a sexual relationship with Reverend Sister Castello, he also does this with the young school boys at Saint Francis School. Reverend Sister Martha is not left out of this sexual immorality as she also maintains a sexual relationship with Doctor James Abe.

Reverend Father Raleigh and the Reverend Sisters believe that, though they are catholic religious leaders, they have to fulfill their biological and sexual instincts. Moreover, they are still human beings, not spirits, even though they are put on cassocks. This belief can be better understood when Reverend Sister Castello says: "Well, well, no sin in liking someone I guess beneath all these cassocks, we are still women, aren't we?" (35).

Reverend Father Raleigh, being gay, makes love to his altar boys and as a result of this act, he protects them even when they commit crimes. Reverend Father Raleigh has been lucky with Emmanuel Lar, and several other boys, but with this young boy whom for almost fifteen minutes they had wriggled for some time, luck ran out on him. Despite the boy's persistence that the Father leaves him, he continues till his urge is satisfied. The boy screams: "No, no, Father! Yeah, God, the boy screams and starts hitting the big man with his fist" (227).

Still, the Father persisted. Desperate to get out of the clutches, the boy digs his nails into the white man's hair and pulls with all his energy. According to the text: "that last exercise brought the man to his senses" (226).

As noted in the text, the innocent boy felt a sort of wetness in his anus which he later discovered to be blood. It was this last incident that exposed the Reverend Father. From the conversation between Dr. James Abe and Frank, it is evident that the news of all that happened has gone around the town. Let's hear them:

James got, into his car, saying, by the way, Frank, what happened to Father Raleigh" I haven't seen him for some time now. Ha! I forgot to tell you, Frank said, moving closer to his friend. Another boy has just been taken to the hospital for bleeding. (229)

This act of sexual immorality perpetrated by Reverend Father Raleigh can be likened to the sexual debasement of Reverend Father Mclaid in Buchi Emecheta's "One is Enough". Through the sexual relationship with Father Mclaid, a Catholic Priest, Amaka conceives and delivers twin boys. According to Egede and Oseghale,

"the actions of both Reverend Fathers betray the oath of celibacy" (76).

Again, he posits that: "Their actions confirm the saying that the hound does not make the Monk" (77).

Apart from the Reverend Father and the two Reverend sisters, other members of the society fictionalized in the text that are also involved in the act of sexual immorality are Dr. James Abe, who not only has Reverend Sister Maltha as his lover, and Elizabeth, the girl that works at the post office, and Dr. Saheed, a specialist in making love to those he feels are cheap. Aside from the sexual immorality perpetrated by these characters, they are also fond of drinking.

Wale Okediran also flays at the rate at which youths get themselves involved in abortion. In the textbook, poverty and sleazy lifestyle coupled with grim ignorance keenly contributed to their perverse livelihood. Our girls, as a result of poverty, have chosen to go into prostitution all in the name of survival. This poverty is a result of total neglect by the government. The outcome of this heinous crime called prostitution, is according to Oseghale, "the procurement of illegal abortion when they get pregnant" (77).

We understand from the text that Alhaji Adamu and Census are two morally bankrupt men who would do anything possible to make money. They are both involved in carrying out activities such as abortion, illegal treatment of children and also collecting large sums of money from them. Alhaji Adamu and Census are partners in crime in that' while Alhaji Adamu treats illegally, Census supplies all the drugs to him that he steals from Faith Medical Centre. Alhaji Adamu only worked for two years as a theatre assistant and set up his illegal clinic. Census is, only a storekeeper.

Alhaji Adam treats his ill-fated patients with expired drugs that are stolen by Census from Faith Medical Centre and Jos Hospital. As a result of this illegal practice by these two dubious characters, so many young girls have lost their lives in this illegal clinic. The deaths of these young girls and children are caused because the people in society are adamant about the advice that it is always better to patronize government hospitals where there are doctors who are competent and experts in their areas of specialization. They prefer quacks to experts because they do not want their immoral sexual acts to be exposed. The action of these women and young girls validates the view expressed by Gloria Chukwukure as quoted by

Oseghale that: “Women remain impervious to advice and warning of doom, they are consequently thrown into social and psychological trauma or experience tragic consequences” (46).

Alhaji Adamu carries out many operations in his illegal clinic that almost take the lives of his patients. He almost cut off the tip of the penis of a boy he circumcised. This circumcision leads to excessive bleeding. The mother of the boy took the boy to Faith Medical Centre where he was attended to by Dr. Abe for treatment. Also, Alhaji Adamu, through an illegal abortion takes the life of Rudi, Alhaji Gidado’s daughter, a girlfriend to Inspector Chike. Let's read this: “The doctor could not detect any pulse or breath in his examination” (47).

The activities of the Nigerian police are not left out of this text. Barely touching on the political and government involvement in all this decadence portrayed in this text, Okediran wittingly masks the foundation of these problems and goes on to talk about the effect of the neglect and non-effectiveness of government policies by criticizing the Nigerian police and their endless corrupt ways. It is chagrin to know that the police who are supposed to be charged with the onus of protecting society against criminals and warring crimes have unfortunately and methodically become perfect criminals. According to Adebayo Philips:

A corrupt police officer is more dangerous than the worst-known civilian criminal. This is because the former is masked and the law is always on its side, choosing to punish whomever it pleases in order to achieve its aims. (1)

In line with the above, Ogoni Okafor opines:

The world today is bedeviled by corruption. There is a prevalence of political, economic, social and religious abnormality. It is so devastating that the entire social life across the African continent is affected in one way or the other. The sophisticated dimensions these social evils are taking obviously require a drastic effort to curb. Literature, especially the satire genre is the instrument with which this task is being undertaken. (1)

Okediran depicts the ugly relationship of the Nigerian police with the masses showing how the innocent are punished and the guilty are set free with the face-off between Dr. James Abe and the D.P.O., Superintendent Kuru. A good example is when Alhaji Adamu kills Alhaji Gidado's daughter through an abortion. This particular girl is the girlfriend of Inspector Chike. Instead of the D.P.O. to have the culprits, Alhaji Adamu and Inspector Chike punished, he asks Gidado to withdraw the case against them from the court in order for him to avoid further calamities from befalling him. For the single fact that Gidado refuses to withdraw the case from the court, his kola nut store is looted and his estate is equally set ablaze. When Gidado reports to the police, the D.P.O. further tells him to expect more problems if he does not withdraw the case. According to Gidado:

Yes, I did. Instead of helping me, the D.P.O. threatened me again... Yes. He told me plainly that I will see more atrocities if I don't withdraw my daughter's case. (170)

Dr. James Abe is also another victim in the text who tries as much as possible to make sure justice is done. When Kudi, Gidado's daughter dies through abortion, Dr. Abe writes a report that incriminates the perpetrators of the act. For this singular act, he is framed up by the police and thrown into detention. He is so maltreated that he retracts his earlier statement indicting the culprits before he was set free.

The corrupt practices portrayed in this text on the part of the Nigerian police are likened to Chinua Achebe's total denouncement of the police in 'No Longer at Ease'. Corruption is portrayed in 'No Longer at Ease' citing the Nigerian customs.

From the moment the book begins, the main character, Obi Okonkwo, is confronted with the issue of bribery. From the moment he arrives at customs to the Point at where he gives in to taking bribes himself, the voice of Achebe lingers in the backdrop through the words.

Another social and moral decadence rampant in the text is aiding and abetting evil practices. The Nigerian police as depicted in the text aid Alhaji Adamu and Census, and even Inspector Chike in carrying out several nefarious activities.

The police in the text provide succor and security for those who ordinarily are supposed to be punished. This aiding and abetting is prominent in the case of Gidado's daughter's death, and the looting and setting ablaze of his estate.

Inspector Chike's corrupt practices make him a very rich man. For example, He has five buses that ply the roads in the country and has also just completed two houses. These are the rewards of corruption, get rich quickly! An explanation of the above in the text reads:

He grew through lucrative corrupt practices in the force. He had about five commercial buses plying the roads in the country while he had just completed two houses in his hometown. All these are on a monthly salary of about six thousand naira. (57)

Amidst all these corrupt practices, Inspector Chike is seen as a devoted and committed Christian who abides strictly to all Catholic doctrines. He contributes generously to the church from his ill-gotten money and as such, Reverend Father Raleigh presents him to the Church as a model worthy of emulation. This, the Father does without questioning the source of his money. Police Inspector Chike is like Eugene in Chimamanda Adichie's 'Purple Hibiscus' who equally donates generously to the Church. This makes Reverend Father Benedict present him to the Church as somebody worthy of emulation. Yet, Eugene, who is generous in the Church, at home abandons his matrimonial responsibilities and also does not care for his aged father, Pa. Nnuku.

Dr. James Abe is like the man in *The Beautiful Ones Are Not Yet Born* by Ayi Kwei Armah, who tries as much as possible to be beautiful only to be infested with corruption when Koosoom finds his place as a fortress after the coup. Dr Abe tries to work according to his professional ethics but the people he works with never allow him to succeed. *Strange Encounters* is an exposition of the societal ills plaguing contemporary African society all in an attempt to expose, correct and eradicate the evils in our society.

Works Cited

Achebe, Chinua. *A Man of the People*. London: Heinemann, 1966. Print.

----- . *No Longer at Ease*. London: Heinemann, 1960. Print.

-----, "The Novelist As A Teacher". G.D. Killam (ed) *African Writer on African Writing*. London: Heinemann, 1973. Print.

Adebayo, Philips. *Corruption in the Nigerian Forces*. Lagos: New World Press, 1999. Print.

Adiche, Ngozi. C. *Americanah*. Lagos: Farafina, 2013. Print.

Agho, Jude. *Standpoints on the African Novel*. Jos: Jubilee Press, 2000. Print.

_____. *From Protest to Assent: Unravelling the African Novel as a Protean Art*. 40th Inaugural Lecture, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma. Ekpoma: Univ. Printing Press, 2011. Print.

_____. *The Novel in Africa: Selected Discourses*. Lagos: Imprint Services, 2013. Print.

Egede, Benji and Anyaoku, Christopher. "Migration and Social Mobility in Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's *Americanah*". *Iroko Journal of Arts*. 16, 2 (2015): 45-46. Print.

Egede, Benji and Francis, Oseghale. "Theme of Social and Moral Decadence in *Wale Okeiran's 'Strange Encounters'*". O.S Odiagbe (ed) *Journal of Global and Social Studies*. Ekpoma: Gplus International, 1, 2 (2011): 72-80. Print.

Idahosa. I. Aiwekho and Agho Jude. A. "Eco-criticism and the Nigerian Novel: A Study of Kaine Agary's *Yellow-yellow* and Tanure Ojaide's *The Activist*". *Iroko Journal of Arts*. 16, 2 (2015): 287 – 295. Print.

Izevbaye, Dennis.S. "The Relevance of Modern Literary Theory in English to Poetry and Fiction in English – Speaking West Africa". An Unpublished PhD Thesis Submitted to the English Department, University of Ibadan. Print.

Nwahunanya, Chinyere. "Introduction: From Boom to Doom- The Niger Delta in Contemporary Nigerian Literature". *From Boom to Doom: Protest and Conflict Resolution in the Literature of the Niger Delta*. Ed. Chinyere Nwahunanya. Owerri: Springfield Publishers Limited, 2011. Print.